

TEACHING MANAGEMENT SCIENCE IN PRE-SCHOOL EDUCATION METHODS OF FORMING THE METHODOLOGY

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Abstract: In this article, management science is organized in preschool education complete information is given about each step. In addition, management is an urgent issue of today.

Key words: preschool education, educator, leader, preschool age children, education.

By the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan on September 9, 2017 measures for fundamental improvement of the pre-school education system signed According to the decision No. PQ-3261 on changes have begun.

The main reason for this is that there are many preschool educational organizations today the existence of problems and the general obsolescence of this system. In this regard official ministries, local government bodies that have been operating approach to preschool education is unsatisfactory. Before school the current state of the infrastructure and material and technical base of educational institutions for children does not allow to ensure full coverage with pre-school education.

In our country, the system of pre-school education organizations is also step-by-step requires updating both in terms of content and form.

The main principles of preschool education and upbringing are as follows:

the opportunity to receive preschool education and upbringing for every child availability;

each child's talents, passions and abilities equality of conditions for development;

education and upbringing of children of preschool age the educational effect of health care, family and preschool education organization unity;

harmony of education and upbringing of children of preschool age;

a personal approach aimed at developing the child's personality; consistency and continuity of pre-school and general secondary education;

democratic and secular nature of education and training;

transparency and openness of the educational process; content, level and volume of preschool education and upbringing developmental characteristics and health status of children of the age of compatibility.

The socio-economic, spiritual and educational changes, progress in the field of science, technology, and technology in the Republic of Uzbekistan and in the process of globalization of information, continuous education system, in particular, before school scientific-methodology of leaders who consistently operate in the management of the educational system the issue of training development is an urgent problem. Pre-school education leader, taking into account the social order placed before the educational system existing shortcomings in the scientific-methodical training of personnel training and improving their skills and organizing independent work on their own can be eliminated by Modern pedagogical theories, education the necessity of arming with technologies was in front of the industry representatives is one of the great tasks. Our observations today are preschool education in managing organizations on a scientific-methodical basis:

- incomplete provision of continuity between the stages of continuous education;
- professional, scientific-methodical training of leading personnel, educational content and its lagging behind methodological support;
- most MTT directors have creative and social activity, ideological and political maturity that it is not at the level of demand;
- Scientific-theoretical and methodical aspect of training system of MTT directors insufficient justification,
- modern pedagogical, information and innovative technologies in this process used to acquire methodological knowledge, skills and qualifications necessary for it is confirmed that there are defects such as lack of attention.

Determining educational goals in preschool educational organizations is based on certain internal and determined by external conditions. In this, the pedagogical environment in the organization and it is necessary to consider the special importance of the state documents establishing the system. That's it along with programs that determine the real educational process are also important. These are external requirements, which are compatible with the specific and existing capabilities of the organization serves as a normative basis for determining the tasks of an educational organization. The professional-pedagogical training of directors of educational organizations is their scientific-theoretical, psychological-pedagogical, scientific-methodical training, ideological-political and consists of spiritual and moral maturity. The structure of professional-pedagogical training parts complement each other, form and develop mutually, of the leader knowledge, skills and qualifications acquired in these components are pedagogical used in activity. Therefore, the scientific and methodological training of kindergarden directors occupies the main place among the components of professional-

pedagogical training. State policy in the field of education defined in the current regulatory documents educational process in educational institutions based on its principles organization and its improvement, as well as the development of management activities is one of the tasks. Kindergarden management in a time of rapid change personnel with all-round intellectual potential, who take their work seriously, har that he acts as a leader who creatively approaches his task the time itself demands it. Because the leader's thinking is deep and broad worldview, modern, pedagogy, psychology, management awareness of science, creative qualities and qualities, faith, behavior cultured, socially active, organizer and entrepreneurship education that he manages determines the future effective activity.

Of the organization The words "Management" and "Manager" are now not only work, but everyday It is also widely used in life, and the state's economy during the transition to the market economy reflects the modern trends of growth.

"Management" is an English word that translates into Russian as management, organization, is translated as leading. So management management, that is, it or economics, finance and management of these activities by the organization or management means management. There are several concepts of management in the scientific literature There are definitions. We will mention 3 of them:

- achieving organizational goals through people working in the organization;
- is a special type of activity, an unorganized group is effective, purposeful turns into a producer group (organization);
- to the goals of the organization through the mediation of labor and material resources are planning, organizing, leading and controlling processes to achieve.

Although these definitions vary, they share 3 common features:

- 1) indicates the existence of a certain goal in management;
- 2) this type of activity is distinguished by a special intellectual character;
- 3) indicates the existence of a management position in the organization.

Management, meaning the concept of management, to the administrative command economy is quite different from the custom control:

The first difference is that management is characteristic of a market economy.

The second difference is that management is an economic method of management. The third difference is that management is the science and art of effective management.

Object of management. Pedagogical management at kundergarden. Republic of Uzbekistan President of September 30, 2017 "Management of preschool education system radical improvement measures Decree No. PF-5198 and "Organization of the Ministry of Preschool Education of the Republic of Uzbekistan in accordance with the Decision No. PQ-3305: preschool education system comprehensive development, healthy and well-educated children aspect was determined.

In particular, as noted in the decree, in our country for the last 20 years the number of state-owned pre-school educational institutions is more than 45 percent Pre-school education of children across the republic has decreased coverage is only 30 percent. Also preschool education The material and technical base of the organizations is almost a response to modern requirements does not give In addition, there are more special secondary schools in pre-school education institutions in the regions in the preparatory groups for school due to the presence of educated personnel that training is not enough, many preschool educational organizations that the buildings do not meet the requirements, especially the coverage of children in the district section it is no secret that it is 18-20 percent.

In this document, the development of a unified state policy in the field of pre-school wide use of foreign experiences in the education of children of the age of to arouse interest in reading books, to organize their healthy and proper nutrition very urgent issues such as improving the quality of medical services received. Pre-school educational institutions of the head and pedagogic staff qualification improvement and retraining are also indicated as extremely important issues, especially noteworthy.

This is the establishment of the Ministry of Preschool Education of the Republic of Uzbekistan by decree It will undoubtedly serve to improve the management system. Now all pre-school education in the state, regardless of departmental affiliation organization will be transferred to this ministry system. A number of important tasks were assigned to the Ministry. Especially before school conducting a unified state policy in the field of education, taking into account advanced foreign experience, preschool children in all aspects intellectual, moral, aesthetic and physical creating conditions for development, state and non-state pre-school education our children at the expense of creating a healthy competitive environment among organizations gradual full inclusion in pre-school educational institutions provision is one of them. In addition, preschool educational institutions are national cultural-historical with educational methodical, didactic materials, games and toys, fiction literature that reflect values and arouse interest in reading books from childhood providing, experienced, highly qualified, professionally

trained pedagogue of the ministry, such as the involvement of personnel and educators in the educational process will be in focus.

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